

Right to Education Act - Some Quality Concerns

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ABSTRACT

The Right to Education Act enacted by India has come in effect from 1st April 2013. It states that every child of the age six to fourteen years shall have a right to free and compulsory education in a neighbourhood school till completion of elementary education. It not only increases enrollment and decrease the cost of education to one and all through inbuilt mechanism. At the same time, its long term goals of RTE need to be met with by due emphasis on quality and not quantity. The focus on the RTE has to shift to quality driven mechanisms that boost the learning outcomes in schools across the country. Even though infrastructure, cost, access and other parameters are important for the success of RTE, quality Teacher Education is the first and foremost condition to ensure the quality of education. Assessment practices, Comprehensive and Continuous Assessment (CCE), new teaching-learning methodologies are some other areas of concern. This paper discusses some issues pertaining to the quality concerns of school education, in the light of RTE.

Keywords: Right to Education (RTE), Quality Concerns, Teacher Eligibility Test (TET), Learning Analytics.

IMPORTANCE OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION AND THE EVOLUTION OF RTE

The education of a country contributes to its economic growth, in overcoming economic and social inequalities, leading to empowerment, reduction of population growth and fertility to child health via mother's schooling. Several international social, economic and human rights resolutions and declarations emphasize the elementary/basic education, Jomtien declaration in 1990 and Dakar declaration in 2000 declared Education and gender parity in education as important goals. The Second Millennium Goal stipulates achieving universal primary education by 2015. Article 45, of the directive principles of the Constitution of India lays stress on free and compulsory elementary education to all the children of India under the age of 14 irrespective of the caste, creed, language, economic conditions, religion, geographical factors, etc. NPE, 1986 re-affirmed the goal of UEE, but did not recognize the right to education. Acharya Ramamurthy Committee in 1992 recommended right to education be included as a fundamental right in part III of the constitution. On August 26, 2009, RTE was enacted as the 86th Constitutional Amendment incorporating Article 21-A of the constitution. and it came into force from April 1, 2010.

PATHETIC CONDITION OF TEACHER EDUCATION AND TET RESULTS

"Who failed in TET; The Teachers, State or the Society?" This is the major question arising in the minds of many educationists. In a shocking statement on the quality of the future generation of teachers, less than 1% of those who took the TET exam on July 12 2012 for the recruitment of Graduate and secondary teachers have passed. Only 2488 candidates passed out of 6, 76,488 in TNTET 2012 exam, with 1735 candidates in Paper I and 713 candidates in Paper II. Results of the supplementary TET conducted in October show that only about 19,200 (2.93 %) of the 6.56 lakh candidates who took the test got through. The performance this time was hugely better than the less than 1 % scored by the TET candidates in the previous test held in July. The teacher aspirants had fared terribly. It reflects the deteriorating quality of the graduates coming into the teaching profession. It appears that many are straying into this area after getting rejected in other careers. The same state prevails in Kerala also.

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THE REASONS FOR THE FAILURE

One of the reasons for so many people failed this test is because it's relatively new. There is not much guidance about the preparation. One fact is that this test will do nothing to increase genuinely valuable teaching, as good teaching is not a function of passing competitive tests. Even the 'best' B Ed course in this country is a farce since it's simply too ambitious. More than training, the teachers need an education, which can, initially, only come with the right attitude of one's immediate teachers, not from the 'comprehensiveness' of a course. Needless to say, we need to first help our teachers become 'humans'.

SKEWED GROWTH PATTERNS OF TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND CORRUPTION

The growth pattern of Teacher Education Institutes (TEIs) is multifarious. In 1995, there were less than 800 TEIs, mostly Government or Government Aided Institutes in India. They were unevenly distributed across states and levels. In 2000, the number rose to 1900 and in 2003, to 2500. But, during 2004 – 08, this number increased by 7273, out of which 2439 TEIs were approved in 2007-08 alone. In 2008, the number of TEIs jumped to around 10,000. Presently in 2012, while there are only 1,178 government teacher training institutes there are as many as 12,689 private ones. This imbalance in the Teacher Educational Institutions causes skewness in the quality of teacher education. Though some TEIs maintain good standards, in most of the self financed TEIs quality is in jeopardy. This cannot be solely due to the corruption on the private side. The corruption in the government mechanisms pervades omnipresent on the following processes such as:

- Inspection from time to time
- Admission procedures
- Recognition from NCTE and affiliation from various Universities
- Examination mechanisms, in particular B.Ed. Practical examinations
- NAAC accreditation
- Staff and Faculty appointments
- Procurement and Utilization of grants from various agencies

Due to corrupt officials and the red-tapism in the Government mechanism in framing and updating modern syllabus and teaching-learning methodologies, it seems teacher education in India is going to bad to worse day-by-day. In such a condition, simply blaming the private colleges alone will not result in the quality of teacher education. Corruption should be abolished and transparency should be maintained during the process. E-Governance may be one of the ways for containing corruption in educational institutions.

DRAWBACKS OF PRESENT ASSESSMENT PRACTICES

The need for meaningfully assessing children's growth in schools features in the RTE. It has reinstated that the academic community shall take into consideration Comprehensive and Continuous Evaluation of the child's understanding to knowledge and his / her ability to apply the same. There is a need of paradigm shift in the assessment process of school education. The earlier over emphasis on cognitive domain has been replaced with a holistic assessment plan providing for development of affective and psychomotor domains of the learners' personality, human values, attitudes, life skills and physical and mental health. The present assessment practices are mostly output-oriented and hardly give emphasis on process of learning of learners. So, modern assessment practices should be used for assessing the students' learning.

DATA EXPLOSION

Internet, computers, mobile devices and enterprise Learning Management Systems (LMSs) form enormous amount of captured, explicit data. Data are collected from explicit student actions,

such as completing assignments and taking exams, student profiles, institutional database and from tacit actions, including online social interactions, extra-curricular activities, clicks, attention/focus heat maps, social network analysis, tweet, facebook update, logging into an LMS, blog-post, posts on discussion forums and other activities that are not directly assessed as part of the student's educational progress. Every click, every Tweet or Facebook status update, every social interaction and every page read online can leave a digital footprint. Additionally, online learning, digital student records, student cards, sensors and mobile devices now capture rich data trails and activity streams. These learner-produced data trails provide valuable insight into what is actually happening in the learning process and suggest ways in which educators can make improvements. Analysis of learner data may also provide insight into which students are at risk of dropping out or need additional support to increase their success and confidence, in the learning process.

MODERN ASSESSMENT PRACTICES

Learning Analytics is a combination of a variety of data – gathering tools and analytic techniques to study student engagement, assess academic progress and predict future performance and spot potential issues. Its main goal is to analyse what is learned to revise curricula, teaching and assessment in real time. Data are collected from explicit student actions, such as completing assignments and taking exams and from tacit actions, including online social interactions, extra-curricular activities, posts on blogs, twitter, discussion forums, etc., and other activities that are not directly assessed as part of the student's educational progress. Learning Management Systems, tools such as Google Analytics and dynamic learning environments generate complex, diverse and abundant information. Learning Analytics mobilize the advances in the power of data mining tools, interpretation and modeling to understand teaching – learning process happening at various learning environments. It enables teachers and schools to tailor educational opportunities to each student's level of need and ability in close-to-real time. Still in its early stages, learning analytics responds to calls for accountability on campuses and aims to leverage the vast amount of data produced by students in academic activities. Pattern Analysis, Social Learning Analytics and Automated Tracking System are relevant for teaching and learning. Signals, Teachscape, Userfy and Mix-panel analytics are some prototype Learning Analytic systems used in some top-ranking Universities. This paper discusses Learning Analytics, its characteristics, its academic applications and some applications currently used in some educational institutions. Data Mining, Portfolio and Rubrics are some other modern mechanisms to assess the students in more sophisticated ways.

TRAINING THE TEACHER

The failure of the vast majority of candidates in the CTET indicates that the teacher education system should be revamped urgently. The B.Ed. teachers could not pass the examination designed to test their fitness for appointment as teachers in government or aided schools. The overall teacher training system has been found wanting for decades. A lot of recommendations have been made by expert panels for improvements. Greater demand for teachers has led to massive quantitative expansion of the number of institutions and courses at various levels without necessary emphasis on infrastructure, faculty qualification and learning resources. State provisioning of elementary education is marked by an attitude of resignation towards the existing system of pre-service and in-service training, which leaves little inspiration for the practitioners to improve.

- The poor performance teacher-trainees in TET, etc., is a clear indicator of the failed assembly-line system of training that exists today.
- The entry-level qualification for training of teachers may be +2 and teacher training can be made as a well-rounded degree programme. It would be worthwhile to invest in a four-year degree programme after senior secondary, or a two-year programme after acquiring a Bachelor's degree.

- The J.S. Verma Commission highlighted the importance of making teacher education a part of the higher education system with necessary rigour and exposure to various integral disciplines.
- The present system is the poor preparation in both the disciplinary and pedagogical domains. Every pre-service teacher education institution should compulsorily have a dedicated school attached to it. It ensures that graduates acquire the necessary competence and skills.
- The regular teacher system should be far superior to distance learning courses.
- Ninety percent of the pre-service teacher education courses are in the non-government sector and the state needs to play a more active role in improving institutional capacity.

CONCLUSION

Making education a fundamental right is surely a step in right direction to address the anomalies and disparities of elementary education in India. It gives legislative framework through which we can question and improve the education system. But RTE alone is not a panacea for all the evils of the present educational system, in particular the school education. The teacher education is the backbone of education system. It should be revamped in a massive way. Corruption, lethargy, greed, resistance to transparency, etc should be addressed first. Without implementing them, it will be very difficult to sustain quality and other fruits of RTE. It depends on the shoulder of all the stakeholders, students, parents, academia and the state.

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